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Research Article

**CAUSATIVE FACTORS FOR REDUCED SOCIAL
INTERACTION IN FEMALES RETIRED FROM
PROFESSIONAL FIELD**¹Dr. Hira Nasir, ²Nabgha Arif, ³Dr. Bilal Sher Khan¹Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College Sialkot²Services Hospital Lahore³Medical officer, DHQ MTI D I Khan.**Abstract:**

Objective: To study the factors responsible for reduced social participation and interaction among elderly female population.

Methods: This study was conducted on retired females of Fatimah Hospital of Hamadan in 2015. Informed consent was taken from all who participated after explaining the objective of study to all of them. Total 50 females were involved. All of them had age more than 60 years. Information was recorded on a questionnaire and factors responsible for it were inquired in detail by the authors. SPSS version 21 was used for data analysis.

Results: there was a significant association between experience and social participation, by overall assessment of responsible factors. 54% females participated in health promotional activities in their area. But significant difference was noted in rate of participation in such activities, p value 0.013.

Conclusion: Retired females from Fatemeih Hospital had sufficient participation in health promotional social activities. However, provision of trainings like confidence building and communication skills building etc. must be ensured.

Keywords: Health Promotion, Community Interactions, Factors, Females.

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INTRODUCTION:

Aging is a process that begins when life starts and it continues throughout one's life. As a person ages, he or she starts living on the memories from past and becomes socially less active. The aim of this study is to find the causes which are responsible for the loneliness and less social participation among elderly individuals so that such causes can be overcome and loneliness and social isolation can be managed[1,2].

Young Ju Jee in a study worked on the factors responsible for such behavior change among elderly. Different aspects like age, gender, past history, previous history of social participation, family support, health status, depression or any psychiatric illness, activities at home, educational status, income etc. were studied and their association with the social behavior and preference of loneliness was evaluated[3].

Social isolation is one of the leading cause of depression and other psychological stress disorders among elderly population. Thus it is important to motivate elderly members of societies to take part in healthy social events in order to improve living condition and to promote better health among old age population[4,5].

METHODOLOGY:

It is cross sectional descriptive study and was conducted after taking informed written consent from all those, who participated. Females more than 60

years of age were enrolled. The questionnaire designed for data collection was reviewed and approved by research committee. The research ethical consideration was well followed during study. The objective of study was explained to all participants by the author. Questionnaires were filled by the authors themselves in order to avoid any error. Data collection was done related to following factors associated with rate of social interactions of females:

Demographic data: this included age, marital status, educational status, history of social participation, rate of participation, and duration of interaction, leisure time.

Other factors: these included factors which facilitate or not the social interaction. The scale was calculated in form of very low, low, high, very high. The questionnaire validity was calculated using internal consistency method and Cronbach's alpha coefficient at level of 0.786. 0.05 was significant p value. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 21.

RESULTS:

The age range was 55 to 65 years. The majority were above 60 years of age. 54% had past history of participation in community activities. 30% had participation for period of 1 to 6 months. 22% had leisure time with them for almost 1-2 hours per day. Study results are expressed in the tabular forms. Table 1 shows all the demographic details of participants.

Variable	Level	Frequency	Percentage
Age	55 to 65	49	98
	More than 65	1	2
	Total	50	100
Educational status	Illiterate	1	2
	Primary and secondary	7	14
	Diploma	14	28
	Academy	28	56
	Total	50	100
Marital status	Single	9	18
	Married	41	82
	Total	50	100
Job status	Retired	47	94
	Govt. employee	3	6
	Private job	0	0
	Total	50	100
Social participation experience	Yes	27	54
	No	23	46
	Total	50	100
Social participation rate	Moderate	15	30
	High	3	6
	Total	27	54
	Without experience	23	46

Duration of participation	Less than 1 month	4	8
	Less than 6 months	11	22
	7 to 12 months	4	8
	More than 12 months	8	16
	Total	27	54
Leisure time	Less than 1 hour	7	14
	1 to 3 hours	26	52
	4 to 6 hours	10	20
	More than 7 hours	7	14
	Total	50	100

Table 1: demographic details.

Variables	Level	Statistics	P value
Age	55 to 65	T=0.469	0.641
	More than 65		
	Total		
Education	Illiterate	F=0.545	0.654
	Primary and secondary		
	Diploma		
	Academy		
Marital status	Single	T=0.814	0.420
	Married		
	Total		
Job status	Retired	T=626	0.534
	Govt. employee		
	Private job		
	Total		
Social participation experience	Yes	T=1.283	0.005
	No		
	Total		
Social participation rate	Moderate	T=0.355	0.705
	High		
	Total		
	Without experience		
Duration of social participation	Less than 1 month	F=0.387	0.013
	Less than 6 months		
	7 to 12 months		
	More than 12 months		
Leisure time	Less than 1 hour	F=0.257	0.856
	1 to 3 hours		
	4 to 6 hours		
	More than 7 hours		
	Total		

Table 2: comparison of risk factors and their statistical significance.

DISCUSSION:

Social interaction is an important responsible for an individual's health and living condition. Elderly individuals prefer loneliness over social interaction due to certain factors like death of spouse, departure of adult offspring, poor health, institutionalization etc.

In a study conducted over Brazilian population it was

estimated that elderly women are 8.5% of total population and according to current growth rate they will become 14% of total population. So better understanding of the facilities and requirements of elderly population for living a healthy life is an important fact to know [6].

A systemic review study was conducted on similar issue by Daneshfar M, et al. it was estimated that

almost 34 to 39% of elderly population suffers severe loneliness due to different factors[7]. 14 factors to help elderly in living a better life were introduced by Jeff Anderson, which were provision of transportation facilities, sense of purpose, promote religious seniors to start taking attendance at the worship places, provide them something to take care of, encourage a positive body image, encourage hearing and vision tests, make adoptive technologies available, notify neighbours, encourage group dining, address incontinence problems, provide a care giver, show more affection towards them etc. [8,9]

CONCLUSION:

Retired females from Fatemeih Hospital had sufficient participation in health promotional social activities. However, provision of trainings like confidence building and communication skills building etc. must be ensured.

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